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4. RISK ASSESSMENT OF DRINKING WATER QUALITY IN AP VOJVODINA

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Objective: The objective of work is to assess the risk of drinking water quality (DWQ) in Autonomous Province of Vojvodina (APV) by using an international risk assessment matrix.

Methods: The data about DWQ were collected in 2016 by 7 regional public health institutions located of APV. The data were unified and evaluated in IPHV, considering 3 different types of drinking water (DW) available for population in APV - purified and disinfected (PDDW), non-purified, but disinfected (NDDW) and non-purified and also non disinfected (NDW). For the risk assessment standardize semi quantitative analyses defined in SRPS EN 15975-2:2015 with 3x3 risk assessment matrix, which assesses the likelihood and consequences of a hazard, rating the risks as low, medium and high, was used. Hazards were identified according to World Health Organization Guideline from 2017.

Results: In APV there are 45 settlements, among which PDDW is provided in 17, NDDW in 40 and NDW in 24. Among settlements with PDDW the low risk was dominant (in 82%), but in settlements with NDDW and NDW the medium and high risk were mostly determinate (in 40% and in 50%, in 46% and 50%, respectively), Consuming and using DW represents high risk for population living in the settlements Kikinda, Ada, Kanjiža, Novi Kneževac, Senta, Čoka, Zrenjanin, Novi Bečej, Pančevo, Bela Crkva, Kovin, Sremska Mitrovica, Inđija, Šid, Subotica, Bačka Topola, Sombor, Kula, Temerin, Vrbas, Bač, Bačka Palanka, Bački Petrovac, Novi Sad.

Conclusion: The systematically prioritizing risk assessment of DW intended for human consumption with proposed standardize methodology is an easily understandable tool which represents the greatest challenge in DW management.

Key words: Risk Assessment; Drinking Water; Public Health; Environmental Medicine